

RS-006-WP2

Prototyping Lab Services – UC02

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2 Document Overview

2.1 Objectives

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (ITSERR1) for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

This document is the Proposal for the Analysis Phase of the MarketPlace for Work Package 2 (DCS).

2.2 Applicable documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[A1]	16/10/2024	VERBALE DI AVVIO ANTICIPATO DELL'ESECUZIONE DEL CONTRATTO PER IL SERVIZIO SERVIZI PER LA CREAZIONE, IL MANTENIMENTO E L'INSTALLAZIONE DI SOFTWARE E SERVIZI ICT DI RICERCA CUSTOMIZZATI – "SOFTWARE LAB", CUP B53C22001770006, CIG B20BDCF4C9, PROT. 167440/2024 DEL 16/10/2024
[A2]	20/06/2022	D.D. n. 11 del 20/06/2022 - a valere dell'avviso pubblico per il "Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca" finanziato nell'ambito PNRR Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Componente 2, "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" - Linea di investimento 3.1, per la tipologia di intervento i. potenziamento di IR presente nel PNIR a priorità alta nell'ambito dell'area ESFRI "Social and Cultural Innovation e contestuale disposizione di impegno di spesa – CIG: B20BDCF4C9"

Table 1 - Applicable Documents

All documents mentioned in this list are available in the Document Repository, section "Applicable Documents".

2.3 Reference documents

Reference documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement and Project scope, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[R1]	20/06/2022	D.D. n. 11 del 20/06/2022 - a valere dell'avviso pubblico per il "Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca" finanziato nell'ambito PNRR Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Componente 2, "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" - Linea di investimento 3.1, per la tipologia di intervento i. potenziamento di IR presente nel PNIR a priorità alta nell'ambito dell'area ESFRI "Social and Cultural Innovation e contestuale disposizione di impegno di spesa – CIG: B20BDCF4C9"
[R2]	16/12/2024	RS-006-WP2
[R3]	30/01/2025	Fincons - ITSERR RS-006-WP2 - WP2 - Prototyping Lab Services - Implementation

Table 2 - Reference Documents

2.4 Acronyms

A list of acronyms frequently used in this document.

Term	Definition
AAI	Authentication Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
D4Science	A platform offering Virtual Research Environments (VREs) and IT components for research purposes
DMP	Data Management Plan
FOSS	Free and Open Source Software
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ITSERR	Re-Inforcement project for the RESILIENCE Research Infrastructure for Religious Studies Research
QA	Quality Assurance
SAD	Software Architecture Documentation
SDP	Software Development Plan
UX/UI	User Experience / User Interface
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

Table 3 – Acronyms

3 Use cases

3.1 UC2: Adapting Vector Similarity Search for Old Church Slavonic Texts

UC4 focuses on the development of a Semantic Search Platform tailored to a historical corpus of Ancient Slavic texts. The corpus consists of approximately 200 documents centered on religious topic, often recounting miraculous phenomena. The aim is to enable semantic-level querying of these texts, allowing users to explore the content beyond simple keyword matches.

The system supports searches based on specific titles, historical time periods, area, and other metadata attributes. Results are returned with highlighted segments that are both lexically and conceptually related to the user's query, offering a more meaningful and context-rich exploration of the corpus.

4 Introduction

This document outlines the full workflow and technical process followed to develop the semantic search platform described in UC2. The tool was specifically created to support semantic exploration of a curated collection of Old Church Slavic texts.

In the sections that follow, we will describe:

- The structure and content of the dataset.
- The full data pipeline including preprocessing, cleaning, chunking and embedding the text using a transformer model.
- How the data and embeddings are stored in Qdrant, a vector database optimized for similarity search.
- The architecture and implementation of the backend API (built with FastAPI).
- The development of the frontend interface (built with React and HeroUI).
- Finally a step-by-step guide for deploying or re-using the platform developed locally.

This documentation aims to ensure the tool can be maintained, extended, and reused beyond the current scope of the project.

4.1 Computational and Hosting Resources

The technical demands of prototype development were addressed through the use of the CNR Barracuda ISTI server, which was used both for embedding generation and database hosting.

4.2 Collaboration with ITSERR Stakeholders

Collaboration with ITSERR stakeholders were a central aspect of the development process. Clear lines of communication has been established, with dedicated points of contact facilitating seamless coordination. Weekly status updates and review sessions ensured progress was reported, challenges addressed, and project alignment maintained. Active participation from research teams ensured that their requirements and feedback were consistently integrated into the prototypes, resulting in solutions that meet the specific needs of the Work Packages.

4.3 Significance and Impact

This research contributes to digital humanities, computational linguistics, and historical text analysis by providing a robust framework for semantic retrieval in ancient languages. The development of a context-aware search system will significantly enhance the accessibility and interpretability of classical texts, supporting scholars in linguistic, philological, and historical inquiries.

5 Dataset Consideration

The dataset used in this project consists of 683 documents, provided in JSON format and merged from two separate sources. Each document is stored under a "Documents" key and contains fields such as Title, Original_title, Latin_title, Century, Area, Language, Source, Notes, and most importantly, Content, which contains the full text in Old Church Slavonic.

The documents span a range of centuries and originate from different regions within the Slavic Orthodox cultural sphere. The accompanying metadata supports advanced filtering and semantic analysis. Among the most useful fields are Century, Area, and Source, which help contextualize the texts both chronologically and geographically.

The primary focus of semantic processing is the Content field. These texts vary significantly in length and complexity. The average document contains approximately 7133 words, with a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 280,403 words. This wide distribution required a robust chunking strategy to make the data suitable for embedding and semantic search.

The texts originate from a variety of repositories and digital libraries. A total of 5 unique source domains are represented in the dataset:

- Azbyka.ru
- Github.com
- Histdict.uni-sofia.bg
- Manuscripts.ru
- Project.phil.spbu.ru

This diversity introduces variability in formatting and textual conventions, a problem that is addressed in Chapter 6 Pre-processing and Cleaning and Chapter 10 Frontend Interface.

6 Pre-processing and Cleaning

The dataset was originally provided in JSON format, containing historical and liturgical texts in Old Church Slavonic. Unlike previous use cases that dealt with Italian legends organized across Excel files, this dataset was semi-structured and unified under a "Documents" key. Each document included a Content field with large amounts of text and accompanying metadata such as Title, Century, Area, Source, and Language.

During the initial pre-processing phase, we experimented with the Classla library—a fork of the Stanza NLP toolkit designed for South Slavic languages (e.g., Bulgarian, Serbian, Macedonian). The goal was to leverage Classla's linguistic features (tokenization, POS tagging, lemmatization) to normalize and parse the Content field. However, Classla struggled with the unique orthographic and historical features of Old Church Slavonic:

- Many tokens were left unrecognized or merged improperly.
- Sentence segmentation was inconsistent, often failing on liturgical punctuation or ancient constructions.
- Memory issues arose when processing longer documents, even after pre-chunking.

A more significant challenge was the presence of PUA (Private Use Area) Unicode characters. These characters are placeholders in the Unicode space reserved for custom fonts or scripts, and they often appeared in the original dataset as "tofu" symbols (e.g., boxes or question marks). These PUA characters were used in legacy typesetting or specialized fonts to represent historical Cyrillic glyphs not covered in standard Unicode.

To address this, we created a PUA-to-Cyrillic mapping table, manually extracted from a reference document. This allowed us to systematically replace each PUA codepoint with its appropriate normalized Cyrillic counterpart. The cleaning script also removed newline escape characters and excessive whitespace.

This pre-processing step was crucial for preparing the data for chunking and semantic embedding. It significantly improved text readability and ensured consistency across documents, especially for downstream models that rely on clear orthography and segmentation for embedding quality.

7 Chunking Technique

To prepare the Old Church Slavonic textual data for semantic embedding and search, we adopted a chunking strategy aimed at segmenting long texts into semantically meaningful units. Chunking is crucial not only for complying with the token limitations of transformer-based models but also for enhancing semantic retrieval accuracy and contextual coherence.

7.1 Classla Approach

We initially attempted sentence segmentation using **Classla**¹, a parser tailored for South Slavic languages such as Bulgarian. The idea was to leverage Classla's part-of-speech tagging and sentence boundary detection. However, this approach was eventually abandoned due to several critical limitations:

- Classla failed to tokenize and segment Old Church Slavonic reliably. The Cyrillic variants used in liturgical texts often differ significantly from modern Slavic orthographies.
- POS tags were inconsistent or missing entirely, leading to poor chunk boundaries.
- Some long documents triggered memory errors.

7.2 SpaCy Approach

Given the Classla issues, we switched to a **rule-based sentence segmentation** approach using **spaCy**'s **multilingual blank model** (`spacy.blank("xx")`). Since there is no dedicated model for Old Church Slavonic in spaCy, we added a lightweight rule-based splitter component to split the text using punctuation-based methodology.

To ensure manageable and semantically coherent segments, we implemented a chunking routine with the following configuration:

- **Target chunk size:** 75 words
- **Minimum size:** 50 words
- **Maximum size:** 100 words
- **Overlap strategy:**
 - For chunks within size bounds, we attached **2 sentences before and after** the chunk to provide contextual continuity.
 - For oversized chunks, we used a sliding window to split the chunk into smaller sub-chunks, each followed by left/right context built from adjacent tokens.

Each chunk record includes:

- The **chunked text**
- The **context_before** (up to 2 preceding sentences)
- The **context_after** (up to 2 following sentences)

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13936406>

² <https://www.bibsonomy.org/bibtex/2d1b3a0bb97e51df1b88d8852cd5ac01>

- All **original metadata fields** from the document source

This approach provided flexibility and ensured that both short and long passages retained enough semantic context to be effectively indexed and retrieved during search.

8 Embedding Methodology

To enable semantic retrieval, each chunk of Old Church Slavonic text was converted into a high-dimensional numerical representation known as an **embedding**. These embeddings allow us to compare textual passages based not on exact keyword overlap but on **semantic similarity**, which is crucial for working with a historic and morphologically rich language like Old Church Slavonic.

Embeddings are central to our semantic pipeline because they allow us to:

- Measure conceptual similarity between phrases, even if they differ in vocabulary.
- Support natural language queries that retrieve thematically related content.
- Enable fast vector-based search via cosine similarity in vector databases like Qdrant.

8.1 Model Selection

Initially, we tested **bert-base-multilingual-uncased**³, a general-purpose multilingual model. However, during the evaluation phase, the results yielded low similarity scores and imprecise semantic matches. This indicated that the model lacked the representational nuance needed for the historical and liturgical nature of our corpus.

As a result, we transitioned to **jinaai/jina-embeddings-v3**⁴, one of the most downloaded and performant multilingual models currently available for text embedding. It is designed for high-quality retrieval use cases and better aligned with our requirement to embed non-standard historical scripts.

8.2 Embedding Pipeline and Storage in Qdrant

The cleaned and chunked dataset was processed in **batches of 16** to optimize GPU memory usage. For each batch:

- Text chunks were tokenized and fed into the Jina model.
- The embedding vector was extracted from the model's [CLS] token (i.e., `outputs.last_hidden_state[:, 0, :]`), cast to float32 to avoid dtype issues.
- A custom **text_to_display** field was constructed using the pattern:

Context_before <mark> Chunk </mark> Context_after

- This format enhances readability and context comprehension in the frontend interface by highlighting the core chunk while preserving its semantic surroundings.
- A payload dictionary was built for each chunk, containing all metadata from the original dataset and the newly created `text_to_display` field
- Each entry was wrapped in a Qdrant PointStruct, assigned a unique UUID, and uploaded to the local Qdrant vector store.

Before uploading, we ensured a clean environment by deleting any existing collection named `old_church_slavonic_collection_with_jina_v3` and recreating it with the correct vector size (determined by the model's hidden size, 1024) and cosine distance as the similarity metric.

³ <https://dblp.org/rec/journals/corr/abs-1810-04805.bib>

⁴ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.10173>

In total, every chunk from the corpus was embedded, wrapped with metadata and context, and indexed in Qdrant. This embedding infrastructure provides the semantic backbone of the search engine, enabling linguists and scholars to explore Old Church Slavonic documents with precision and contextual awareness, even when queries do not directly match the original wording.

9 Backend Development

The backend serves as the core engine of the semantic search platform. It acts as the bridge between the **Frontend Interface** where users input their queries and **Qdrant** vector database where the embeddings and metadata are stored.

Having a dedicated backend layer ensures that the frontend remains lightweight and agnostic of implementation details, complex operations like embedding user queries, validating inputs and interfacing with different models/collections are centralized and controlled. Furthermore, the system is modular and scalable, making it easy to add new models, corpora or business logic without disrupting the frontend or data layer.

The backend is implemented using **FastAPI**, a high-performance Python web framework, it exposes a single endpoint **POST /search**. This endpoint performs the following tasks:

Receives a user query along with parameters like corpus selection, model name, top-k results and similarity threshold.

1. Validates the query length to ensure it fits within the token limit of the selected model.
2. Selects the correct model and Qdrant collection based on the corpus and model parameters.
3. Generates an embedding for the query using the appropriate model.
4. Searches the Qdrant vector store, returning the top relevant chunks based on cosine similarity.
5. Filters results by threshold, returning only those above the requested similarity score.

Packages results into a clean response format including the text to display, semantic similarity score and all associated metadata.

The system currently supports multiple corpora and embedding models:

Corpus	Model	Qdrant Collection Name
Old Church Slavic Mapping	jinaai/jina-embeddings-v3	old_church_slavonic_collection_with_jina_v3
Old Church Slavic Without Mapping	jinaai/jina-embeddings-v3	old_church_slavonic_collection_with_jina_v3_without_mapping

Each model has its own dedicated handler function allowing flexibility to extend to new dataset or models in the future.

To support experimentation and performance evaluation of preprocessing strategies, two separate Qdrant collections were created: `old_church_slavonic_collection_with_jina_v3` and `old_church_slavonic_collection_with_jina_v3_without_mapping`. Both collections were built from the same base dataset but differ in the application of the PUA Unicode character mapping introduced during the pre-processing phase. The `with_jina_v3` collection contains texts that have undergone PUA normalization, while the `without_mapping` version retains the original unnormalized content. This distinction was implemented to assess whether correcting the PUA characters improves semantic embedding and retrieval quality. Both collections used the `jinaai/jina-embeddings-v3` model for embedding creation, ensuring that the only difference between them lies in the pre-processing step.

10 Frontend Interface

The frontend provides an intuitive, user-friendly interface that allows researchers and users to interact with the semantic search engine without needing any technical expertise. It is the entry point to the system, offering tools for query input, corpus selection, result filtering, and metadata exploration.

While the backend handles query processing and semantic retrieval, the frontend is responsible for:

- Collecting input from users.
- Displaying search results in a clear and accessible way.
- Allowing filtering based on metadata
- Providing real-time feedback on search progress or errors

The technologies used for the implementation of the Frontend interface are:

- **React:** A Javascript framework used to build the dynamic interface.
- **HeroUI:** A component library used for modern, responsive UI elements (inputs, accordion, buttons, etc.).
- **Tailwind CSS:** Provides clean utility-based styling.

The Frontend interface provides the following key features:

- **Query panel**
 - Textarea to input the search query
 - Select boxes to choose the corpus and the corresponding model
 - Similarity Score and Top-K Results inputs to let users define the strictness of the results. And enable filtering based on semantic proximity
 - Search button to initiate the request
- **Filter Panel**
 - Dynamically populated autocomplete filters based on metadata returned from the backend.
 - Filter and Reset buttons allow users to refine or reset their search easily.
- **Results Display Panel**
 - Results are shown as listbox items, paginated in groups of 5.
 - Each item displays the highlighted chunk of text using `<mark>` tags to emphasize the matched portion.
 - An Accordion expands to reveal metadata for each result.

To ensure accurate visual rendering of Old Church Slavonic texts, the frontend applies specific fonts dynamically based on the domain listed in the Source metadata field. Since the documents were aggregated from various online repositories each relying on its own typographic conventions to represent extended Cyrillic and historical glyphs this approach preserves the visual fidelity of the original sources. The platform supports five custom fonts, each associated with a corresponding domain:

- **Triodion** font for texts from **azbyka.ru**⁵
- **github-ocs** font for texts from **syntacticus.org**⁶
- **cb10u** font for texts from **histdict.uni-sofia.bg**⁷
- **menaion** font for texts from **manuscripts.ru**⁸

⁵ <https://azbyka.ru/>

⁶ <https://syntacticus.org/>

⁷ <https://histdict.uni-sofia.bg/>

⁸ <http://manuscripts.ru/>

- **AGIO** font for texts from **project.phil.spbu.ru**⁹

This domain-aware font assignment ensures that special characters unique to Old Church Slavonic are correctly displayed in the user interface, enhancing readability and historical authenticity.

⁹ <https://project.phil.spbu.ru/scat/page.php?page=project>

11 Final Architecture

The overall system architecture is composed of three main components that work together to deliver a seamless semantic search experience:

- **Frontend interface**
The user interface that allows researches to input queries, choose models, apply filters, and view results.
- **Backend**
The intermediary layer that handles use input, encodes the query, communicates with vector database and returns results.
- **Qdrant Vector Database**
Stores all pre-computed embeddings of the dataset along with associated metadata, which handles fast similarity-based retrieval of relevant passages.

The frontend communicates with the backend through a single `/search` POST endpoint. This tightly-coupled interaction ensures that all query logic and model-specific behavior remains centralized and secure in the backend.

The following is a step-by-step breakdown of what occurs when a user performs a search:

- 1. User interaction:**
 - a. The user enters a natural language query into the frontend.
 - b. They select the desired corpus and embedding model.
They adjust search parameters such as top-K results and similarity threshold.
- 2. API request:**
 - a. The frontend send a post request to `/search` endpoint.
 - b. The request payload contains parameters such as *query, corpus, model, threshold, top_k*.
- 3. Backend Processing:**
 - a. The backend receives the request and routes it to the correct handler function based on the selected corpus/model.
 - b. The appropriate transformer model is loaded.
 - c. The query is encoded into a semantic embedding vector.
 - d. The backend verifies that the input is within the token limit for the model (e.g., 512 tokens).
- 4. Qdrant Search:**
 - a. The backend send a vector similarity search request to Qdrant using the query embedding.
 - b. Qdrant returns the top-k most similar text chunks from its indexed collection.
- 5. Filtering and Formatting:**
 - a. The backend filters results based on the threshold
 - b. Each result is packaged with highlighted text, semantic similarity score and Metadata.
- 6. Response to Frontend:**
 - a. The filtered and formatted results are sent back to the Frontend in JSON format.
 - b. The frontend dynamically displays the results, including context and allows the user to expand metadata and apply additional filters.

12 Deliverables

This chapter describes the final deliverables made available through the project and provides a comprehensive guide to set up, run, and test the full semantic search platform.

The main goal of this stage is to ensure that the platform is completely reusable and that other developers or researchers can download the repository and deploy the system locally with minimal effort

12.1 Repository Structure

The repository is organized in a modular and intuitive way, separating concerns between data processing, backend logic, and the frontend interface. Below is an overview of the structure:

```
.
├── itserr-fincons-backend/
│   └── app.py
├── itserr-fincons-frontend/
│   └── (React + HeroUI components)
├── data-processing/ # Data cleaning, chunking, embedding scripts
│   ├── Italian/
│   │   ├── process_original_dataset.py
│   │   ├── chunking.py
│   │   ├── embedding.py
│   │   └── dataset/
│   │       └── original/
│   │           └── Database Leggende di Fondazione dei Santuari - versione per FINCONS prototipo.xlsx
│   └── Slavic/
│       ├── process_original_dataset.py
│       ├── chunking.py
│       ├── embeddings.py
│       └── dataset/
│           └── original/
│               └── ocs_data_merged_full_2025_05_23.json
├── setup_italian.sh
├── setup_slavic.sh
├── requirements_italian.txt
├── requirements_slavic.txt
└── README.md
```

12.2 Step-by-Step Guide

The following steps explain how to set up and execute the project locally.

12.2.1 Prerequisites

Before proceeding, ensure that the following software is installed in the system:

- Python 3.8+
- Docker
- Node.js + npm (to run the frontend application)

12.2.2 Start Qdrant Instance

To enable semantic search, a local instance of Qdrant must be started. The following Docker command will launch a Qdrant container listening on port 6333:

```
Docker run -p 6333:6333 -v $(pwd)/qdrant_storage:/qdrant/storage qdrant/qdrant
```

If Qdrant is hosted on a different machine or uses a different port, make sure to update the connection settings in `data-processing/Slavic/embedding.py` and `itserr-fincons-backend/app.py`.

12.2.3 Run the Setup Script

The repository contains a helper script called `setup_slavic.py` which performs all the necessary steps to prepare the data and generate embeddings:

To execute it:

```
chmod +x setup_slavic.sh
./setup.sh
```

12.2.4 Start the backend

Once the data has been uploaded to Qdrant, the FastAPI backend can be started using the following commands:

```
cd itserr-fincons-backend
python app.py
```

This starts the backend server on `http://localhost:8002`

12.2.5 Start the Frontend

To launch the user interface, run the following commands:

```
cd itserr-fincons-fronted
npm install
npm run dev
```

The frontend will be available at `http://localhost:5173`

13 Conclusions and Next steps

This project has delivered a functional and extensible semantic search platform tailored for Old Church Slavonic textual corpora. By integrating a modern frontend interface, a FastAPI-based backend, and a high-performance Qdrant vector database, users can explore large and linguistically complex historical texts through conceptually driven queries. The system enables passage-level semantic retrieval, enriched with contextual metadata and dynamically styled fonts that accurately reflect the typographic conventions of each source domain.

From an initial qualitative evaluation, the platform demonstrates promising results in retrieving semantically meaningful sentences for many input queries. However, qualitative analysis reveals that in certain cases, the retrieved results fall short of expectations in terms of semantic proximity. This disparity can be attributed to multiple factors:

- **Model Limitations:** The selected embedding model (*jinaai/jina-embeddings-v3*) is multilingual but not explicitly trained on historical or Old Church Slavonic data. While it performs reasonably well for modern Cyrillic scripts, it lacks grounding in ancient glyphs, orthographic variants, and domain-specific semantics.
- **Incomplete Unicode Normalization:** Despite our application of a detailed PUA (Private Use Area) Unicode mapping strategy, some characters remain unmapped or inconsistently rendered. These unresolved characters likely introduce noise into the embedding space, weakening the semantic coherence of certain chunks.
- **Disjoint Between Text Representation and Embedding:** The glyph-correct rendering introduced via font mapping in the frontend is purely visual and applied *after* embeddings are generated. As such, while the user interface displays historically accurate text, the model itself never “sees” these characters during vector encoding. This semantic mismatch limits the model’s ability to reason meaningfully about some passages.
- **Domain Complexity and Script Variants:** Old Church Slavonic exhibits high orthographic variance, even across texts from the same century. Without normalization or dialect-specific training, the model may incorrectly segment, tokenize, or interpret some sequences, leading to embeddings that are only superficially similar.

It is important to stress that these observations are based on qualitative assessments. As there are currently no robust automatic translation or semantic evaluation tools for Old Church Slavonic, the validity of retrieved results ultimately requires verification by domain experts. Their linguistic and historical expertise remains essential for interpreting and validating the system’s outputs.

13.1 Next Steps

Model Adaptation or Fine-Tuning: Training or fine-tuning a model on domain-specific data could substantially improve retrieval accuracy. Even a multilingual encoder adapted with historical Slavonic texts might bridge the semantic gap caused by out-of-domain tokens.

Character-Level or Subword Embedding Models: Exploring models that operate on finer linguistic units (e.g., character-level transformers) may mitigate the issue of rare or unmapped glyphs, improving semantic generalization across orthographic variation.

Error-Driven Analysis: A systematic review of incorrect or irrelevant results could help isolate specific linguistic features that degrade retrieval quality, informing the design of future preprocessing or normalization techniques.

Scientific Evaluation Framework: While the current validation is primarily qualitative, a key next step is the definition of a **scientific evaluation methodology**. This should involve structured collaboration with domain experts, the formulation of ground truth datasets, and the adoption of repeatable metrics (e.g., precision, recall, relevance judgments) to assess the retrieval quality

objectively. This will complement the preliminary assessments and provide stronger evidence for the model's effectiveness.

This foundation serves not only as a semantic access point to Old Church Slavonic texts but also as a modular framework ready to support other historical corpora with similar linguistic and representational challenges.